

Electrochemical reactions at sacrificial electrodes. Part-XIX. Synthesis of antimony(III) alkoxides

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Abstract : The electrochemical reactions of methanol, ethanol, propan-1-ol, butan-1-ol, pentan-1-ol, hexan-1-ol, heptan-1-ol, octan-1-ol, nonan-1-ol and decan-1-ol have been carried out at sacrificial antimony anode. The products isolated from the anode compartment have been identified by elemental analysis and infrared spectral studies and are found to be antimony(III) alkoxides. All these reactions proceed with high current efficiencies.

Keywords : Alkoxide, antimony, electrochemical technique.

Electrochemical technique has been used in synthetic organic¹, inorganic² and green³ chemistry. The important advantages of this technique include single step and direct method to carry out oxidation and reduction. Metal alkoxides, in general, have several applications in electronic ceramics⁴. The alkoxides of antimony are known to be used as catalysts in a number of polymerization reactions, in addition, these have also fungicidal and insecticidal activity⁵ and are employed as precursors⁶ for the deposition of thin films of Sb_2O_3 and Sb_6O_{13} . In view of these important applications of the alkoxides and in continuation to our interest in synthetic electrochemistry⁷, we report in this communication the synthesis and characterization of antimony(III) alkoxides.

Experimental

Acetonitrile was kept over phosphorus pentoxide for 24 h and then double distilled. Freshly distilled acetonitrile was used as solvent in all these reactions. Tetrabutylammonium chloride (Reidal pure) was crystallised from conductivity water and dried under reduced pressure at 100 °C. It was then used as supporting electrolyte in all these reactions.

An H-type cell made of pyrex glass in which the cathode and anode compartments were separated from each other by a sintered glass disc of G-3 porosity, was used as the reaction vessel. Both compartments were provided with two openings; one for guard tube and the other for electrode. Platinum foil ($1.0 \times 1.0 \text{ cm}^2$) and antimony plate ($2 \times 10 \times 0.2 \text{ cm}^3$) were used as cathode and anode respectively. Direct current was obtained with the help of Toshniwal electrophoresis power supply. The

electrolytic solution in the anode compartment was stirred efficiently using magnetic stirrer.

5.0 mL of alcohol, 1.0 g of tetrabutylammonium chloride and 250 mL of freshly distilled acetonitrile were taken in the H-type cell. Antimony metal electrode was dipped in the anode compartment and platinum foil in the cathode compartment and outlets were sealed after fitting the guard tubes. Necessary connections were made with power supply and potential across the electrodes was then adjusted so that a current of 20 mA passed through the solution. The cell can be represented as :

where $Sb_{(+)}$ is antimony anode, $Pt_{(-)}$ is platinum cathode, Bu_4NCl is supporting electrolyte and ROH is alcohol used in systems.

The electrolysis was carried out with continuous stirring in the anode compartment. After conducting electrolysis for ten hours, the product was filtered, washed with hot acetonitrile and dry ether and finally dried under vacuum.

Accurately weighed amount of the product (about 200 mg) was heated to dryness four times with 5.0 mL of fuming nitric acid. The dry mass was then dissolved in 5.0 mL concentrated hydrochloric acid and water and diluted to 100 mL in measuring flask. Using this solution, antimony contents in the products were estimated iodometrically⁸.

Melting point of all these products was recorded using electrical device with heating rate of 5 °C per minute.

Infrared spectra of the products have been recorded using potassium bromide pellets in the region of 4000–450 cm^{-1} using Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer (RXI). The current efficiencies (gram equivalents of metal dissolved per Faraday) of all these systems were determined by conducting electrolysis of above systems under similar conditions but at constant potential for two hours. The solution in anode compartment was taken out. The anode compartment of the cell and anode was washed three times with acetonitrile. The solution of the anode compartment along with its washings was distilled in film evaporator until 10 mL of contents was left in the flask. The contents were then transferred to a beaker and heated to dryness. Antimony contents were then determined in the dry mass as discussed above. The ratio of experimental and theoretical antimony contents gives the current efficiency of the system.

Results and discussion

Electrolysis of methanol, ethanol, propan-1-ol, butan-1-ol, pentan-1-ol, hexan-1-ol, heptan-1-ol, octan-1-ol, nonan-1-ol, decan-1-ol have been carried out at sacrificial antimony anode and inert platinum cathode. As the purpose of the present studies is to explore the use of the electrochemical technique as a synthetic tool, the electrolysis has been conducted at quite high potential so that sufficient amount of the product may be produced. Solvent and supporting electrolyte remain unaffected as long as highly electroactive species (alcohols and antimony in these systems) are present in the solution⁹. The electrolysis characteristics of these systems are recorded in Table 1.

It has been observed that the electrochemical products are quite stable and are not much affected by air. All

these products are insoluble in various organic solvents such as methanol, ethanol, benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, *N,N*-dimethyl formamide, dimethyl sulphoxide, acetone etc. The molecular weight of these compounds could not be determined due to their insoluble behaviour. These products do not melt up to 300 °C, however, it was observed that these compounds change their colour in the temperature range of 200 to 250 °C which indicates that these products may decompose around this temperature.

Antimony contents in all these products were determined iodometrically⁸. Microanalysis for carbon and hydrogen contents of some of the products have also been carried out. All the analytical data conform to the molecular formula $\text{Sb}(\text{OR})_3$. The relevant data are summarized in Table 1.

Infrared spectral data of all these products reveal that there is no absorption band corresponding to hydroxyl group¹⁰ in the region of 3600–3200 cm^{-1} . However, the characteristic bands appear in the region of 1160–1000 cm^{-1} and 560–543 cm^{-1} . Stretching mode of $\nu(\text{Sb}-\text{O})$ in case of antimony alkoxides appears in the region of 612–540 cm^{-1} . The presence of bands in the region of 560–543 cm^{-1} in the present products can thus be assigned to $\nu(\text{Sb}-\text{O})$ stretching vibrations.

Infrared data of metal alkoxides show the existence of two types of $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})\text{M}$ absorption bands¹¹. The terminal alkoxide groups show absorption bands in the region of 1160–1060 cm^{-1} and bridged alkoxide groups show absorption band in the region of 1060–1000 cm^{-1} . Infrared spectra of the present electrochemical products show absorption bands in both these regions. It has been observed that the bands due to bridged alkoxide groups

Table 1. Electrolysis characteristics, analytical and other related data of electrolysis of alcohols at antimony anode

Alcohol	Potential (V)	Electricity passed (Coulombs)	Product	Colour	Elemental analysis (%) :			Current efficiency (gram equivalent/Faraday)
					Found (Calcd.)			
					Sb	C	H	
Methanol	50	720	$\text{Sb}(\text{OCH}_3)_3$	White	57.2 (56.6)	12.2 (12.8)	2.30 (2.21)	0.90
Ethanol	30	720	$\text{Sb}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_3$	White	47.2 (47.4)	28.1 (28.3)	3.82 (3.45)	0.86
Propan-1-ol	30	720	$\text{Sb}(\text{OC}_3\text{H}_7)_3$	White	42.6 (41.1)	32.4 (32.2)	4.22 (4.10)	0.95
Butan-1-ol	50	720	$\text{Sb}(\text{OC}_4\text{H}_9)_3$	White	36.5 (35.7)	–	–	0.76
Pentan-1-ol	50	720	$\text{Sb}(\text{OC}_5\text{H}_{11})_3$	White	31.9 (31.8)	42.3 (41.1)	6.24 (5.60)	0.96
Hexan-1-ol	50	720	$\text{Sb}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_{13})_3$	White	28.8 (28.6)	46.2 (47.9)	7.20 (8.90)	0.60
Heptan-1-ol	50	720	$\text{Sb}(\text{OC}_7\text{H}_{15})_3$	Light brown	27.3 (26.0)	49.5 (49.0)	8.22 (8.15)	0.55
Octan-1-ol	40	720	$\text{Sb}(\text{OC}_8\text{H}_{17})_3$	Light brown	22.8 (23.9)	–	–	0.75
Nonan-1-ol	50	720	$\text{Sb}(\text{OC}_9\text{H}_{19})_3$	Light brown	22.7 (22.1)	53.4 (54.9)	9.82 (10.3)	0.84
Decan-1-ol	50	720	$\text{Sb}(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_{21})_3$	Light brown	21.3 (20.5)	56.7 (57.8)	10.1 (10.6)	0.95

are strong as compared to those of terminal groups. However, the relative intensity of the bands due to bridged alkoxide groups decreases as the size of alkyl group in the alcohol increases. In the case of bulky groups bridging decreases, due to steric hinderance¹². Infrared data show bridging in all the products thus indicating that these alkoxides are polymeric in nature. The insoluble behaviour of all these products in various organic solvents and high melting point also support the polymeric nature of all these products.

Current efficiencies of all these systems have also been determined and are listed in Table 1. The current efficiencies of these systems are quite high, except for hexan-1-ol and heptan-1-ol systems. High current efficiency of these systems show that the formation of antimony(III) alkoxides are the predominant reactions of these systems. Current efficiencies of hexan-1-ol and heptan-1-ol systems have been determined at different intervals of time in order to throw light on the reason of low current efficiencies. All the data are recorded in Table 2. Perusal of Table 2 reveals that the current efficiencies are quite high initially but decrease as time of electrolysis increases. The decrease in current efficiencies with time is due to the reason that the products formed in these systems form a protective layer on the electrode surface (antimony anode) and thus inhibit the further dissolution of metal and hence act as corrosion inhibitors¹³. The reaction scheme may be given as :

At cathode :

At anode :

The present studies provide a new route for the synthesis of antimony(III) alkoxides which have several applications in industry and laboratory. It is a single pot and direct synthetic method associated with very high current efficiencies.

Table 2. Current efficiencies of electrochemical reactions of hexan-1-ol and heptan-1-ol at antimony anode at different intervals of time

Alcohol	Time (h)	Current efficiency (gram equivalent/Faraday)
Hexan-1-ol	1.0	0.90
	1.5	0.85
	2.0	0.60
Heptan-1-ol	1.0	0.95
	1.5	0.83
	2.0	0.75

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